

Robotic Arm Control for Dice Manipulation using Computer Vision and Tactile Sensing

Eleonora Fontana*, Chiara Lambranzi^{†||}, Seyyed Masoud Kargar[‡], Antonella Imperato[§] and Rana Umair Hameed[¶]

*Department of Information Engineering and Research Centre “E. Piaggio”, University of Pisa, Pisa, Italy
Email: eleonora.fontana@phd.unipi.it

[†]Department of Electronics, Information and Bioengineering (DEIB), Politecnico di Milano, Milano, Italy

^{||}XoLab, Department of Advanced Robotics, Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia (IIT), Genova, Italy

[‡]Department of Mechanical, Energy, Management and Transportation Engineering (DIME), University of Genova, Genova, Italy

[§]Department of Electrical Engineering and Information Technologies, University of Naples Federico II, Naples, Italy

[¶]Department of Industrial Engineering, University of Trento, Trento, Italy

Abstract—In the pursuit of advanced robotics and intelligent machine capabilities, this abstract explores the solutions adopted in a robotic challenge. Given a specific number as the goal, the objective entailed manipulating the dice to precisely exhibit the face corresponding to that specified value. The approach focused on four key aspects: design, control, vision, and perception. A gripper structure was designed and 3D-printed, control strategies were implemented to achieve the goal, a calibrated camera was utilized for dice recognition and value extraction, and sensors were integrated onto the gripper fingers for precise feedback during manipulation. This abstract explores the methodologies applied for each of these aspects and presents results and conclusions, where it is shown how the goal is achieved minimizing the number of iterations and the total time required.

Index Terms—Robotic Challenge, DRIMS2, Dice Manipulation

I. INTRODUCTION

In the realm of robotics and intelligent machines, the ability to manipulate objects with precision and dexterity remains a fundamental challenge [1], [2]. Among these challenges, the task of manipulating a seemingly simple object, such as a six-sided dice, presents an intricate puzzle that requires the seamless integration of mechanical, control, visual, and sensor-based approaches. In this paper, will be investigated the innovative techniques and methodologies, employed by our team, to tackle this challenge during the 1st Doctoral Summer School on Robotics and Intelligent Machines, which was held this year from August 30 to September 5 at the Scuola Internazionale di Alta Formazione (SIAF) in Volterra, Pisa, Italy. Our main goal was the manipulation of the dice, in order to display one of its faces with any desired number. To accomplish this task, a multidisciplinary journey was embarked upon, encompassing finger design, strategic control, vision-based perception, and sensor integration. The steps of our proposed solution to the challenge are shown in Fig.1. The subsequent section of this paper will delve into each of these components, providing a

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Fig. 1: Steps of the Implemented Solution

Fig. 2: (a) CAD model of the fingertips mounted onto the wrist; and (b) The printed fingertip

comprehensive understanding of the techniques, challenges, and outcomes of the dice manipulation project.

II. METHODOLOGY

The challenge took place in a controlled environment where each team had access to an YuMi manipulator (ABB, Switzerland). Additionally, a fixed OAK-D Pro camera (Luxonis, USA) was positioned parallel to the table, and force sensors were available for integration onto the gripper fingers.

A. 3D Design

The discussed solution commenced with the design and development of a specialized robotic finger, carefully engineered to be compatible with a robotic arm. The design objectives for the finger were clear: maximize the distance between fingers, optimize the finger’s form to accommodate sensors, and ensure ease of installation. These considerations were paramount, given the specific constraints dictated by the task. Notably, we were faced with the challenge of maintaining a distance between the fingers that allowed for effective grasping while accommodating the sensor thickness. The CAD and prototype of the final designed model is shown in Fig.2

Fig. 3: Control Strategy Flowchart

B. Control

Control strategy played a pivotal role in our approach. We based our strategy on two fundamental assumptions: first, the sum of opposite faces of a dice always equates to seven, and second, two face identifications are sufficient to map all the faces of the dice. These assumptions laid the groundwork for our strategy, which consisted of three core primitives: picking and placing, flipping the dice by 90° , and performing z-axis rotations. The detailed strategy is shown in Fig.3. At first, Primitive 1 (pick and place) is executed so that the dice is placed in a convenient location for manipulation, *i.e.* the center of the workspace. Subsequently, the identification of the top face (and implicitly of the bottom) is performed. If the goal is the bottom face Primitive 2 (flip by 90°) is performed. Alternatively, after a single flip a second camera identification is performed: thus, all the faces can be mapped. If the top or the bottom face is the goal the previous steps are repeated, otherwise Primitive 3 (z-axis rotation) is performed. By combining these three primitives, it is possible to achieve the goal with the exact number of moves required. The control strategy was centered on the utilization of ROS (Robot Operating System) and Pilz Industrial Motion Planner for inverse kinematics solving. The whole approach ensured the necessary repeatability and accuracy for the challenge.

C. Vision

The vision task can be divided into three steps: calibration, detection, and identification [3]. Calibration involved the determination of the dice pose with respect to the robot reference frame through the transform $T_d^r = T_w^r T_c^w T_d^c$, that is shown in 4.A and uses the homogeneous matrices: T_d^c , that is built using intrinsic camera parameters; T_c^w , that is obtained through checkerboard method using the PNP-RANSAC algorithm [4]; T_w^r that is the inverse of the provided matrix T_r^w . Dice detection is described in 4.B-D: given the detected contours c_i , the squareness condition is $c_w/c_h \sim 1$, with c_w, c_h respectively the width and height of the minimum rectangle that can wrap the detected contour, and the result of this operation is the

Fig. 4: A) Whole setup with dice d , camera c , checkerboard w and robot r ; B) section of the image acquired by the camera; C) yellow mask, erosion and dilation applied on B); D) minimum rectangle of contour that satisfies squareness condition; E) crop and binarize, contour detection with circularity condition.

dice pose in the image space. Number identification 4.E is performed only when the dice is placed in the convenient location for the manipulation, to increase the robustness of the recognition. The circularity condition is $4\pi c_a/c_p^2 \sim 1$, with c_a, c_p area and perimeter of the considered contour.

D. Perception

To enhance manipulation capabilities, sensors were integrated onto the gripper fingers. Thus, perception encompassed interfacing with sensors, data processing, and communication with external systems. Reading data streams, processing outputs into meaningful arrays, and calibrating sensor data were essential steps in this phase. Integration with an external machine via UDP communication enabled real-time feedback and control, paving the way for advanced operations, such as slip detection.

III. CONCLUSION

In the pursuit of mastering dice manipulation through the synergistic blend of finger design, vision, and sensor integration, a successful integration of all these components was presented, leading our team to win the challenge during the 1st Doctoral Summer School on Robotics and Intelligent Machines. The comprehensive approach proved to be highly effective, consistently and accurately manipulating the dice to display the target number minimizing the allocated time frame, numbers of iterations and identifications.

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